

Acharya Ray and Chemical Research in Modern India

J. N. Ray

Acharya Ray is rightly regarded as the father of chemical research in modern India. But for his tenacity, the advance of chemical education in this country would have been delayed for a long time. In order to judge the real contribution he made in this regard, it is necessary to recall that he was born in 1861, three years after the Indian Mutiny. The state of the country in every direction then was probably at the lowest ebb. The historians have assessed the real significance of the Mutiny in which all kinds of forces, progressive and reactionary, were drawn together. It is now regarded that the failure of the Mutiny was a blessing in disguise. The country woke up to the realisation that the real salvation of India lay in the pursuit of Western Arts and Sciences. It was at this time that Acharya Ray was born. The Calcutta University had been established in 1857 and in his boyhood, education in the country had not been properly organised. When a student in the Metropolitan College, he had to attend the science lectures at the Presidency College, which was the only institution where arrangements for imparting rudimentary education in science existed. It is therefore no wonder that he left for Edinburgh in 1882 before his graduation, availed by the Gilchrist scholarship which was awarded to him in that year. Though he was of literary bent of mind, he realised that the future of this country lay in pursuing science. He came under the tutelage of Professor Crum-Brown who was regarded as a great teacher. In 1885, he obtained the B.A. and in 1888, the D.Sc. degree of the Edinburgh University. His thesis was on Periodic Law. He obtained the Hope Prize and was elected Vice-President of the Edinburgh University Chemical Society. He returned to India in 1888 and secured a junior post at the Presidency College. He accepted this post as it was possible to do some research work; though the equipment was of an elementary nature yet it was far superior to other institutions which had little or no equipment at all.

He published his first work from the Presidency College on 'Conjugated sulphates and isomorphous mixtures of the copper-magnesium group' in 1891. Before this, he was engaged in determining adulteration of foodstuffs—a subject of public interest at that time in Calcutta. The results were published in the *Journal of Asiatic Society of Bengal*¹².

In 1896, he was able to isolate mercurous nitrite, a real land-mark in his career. It may be recorded that this discovery was made when he was engaged in gas-analysis. In his attempted purification of an impure sample of mercury, the first indication was obtained for the formation of mercurous nitrite. This was obtained as yellow thin crystals when dilute nitric acid containing 13-14% of N_2O_5 reacted with mercury in the cold⁵ (*J. Asiatic Soc.*, 1896). The journal of Asiatic Society can scarcely be called a scientific journal, yet this paper was noticed by the *Nature*. The results were later on published in detail in the *Journal of the Chemical Society, London*. Subsequently a neat method was devised for the preparation of mercuric hyponitrite¹³. This consisted in reacting mercuric nitrite with potassium cyanide, the latter was oxidised to cyanate, and the nitrite was reduced to hyponitrite. He then began an investigation on the preparation of nitrites of alkaline earths,

These were prepared in a pure state for the first time and it was noticed that magnesium nitrite was the least stable and formed a link between the nitrites of Zn and Cd and those of Ca, Ba and Sr.^{18,21,24-26} The double nitrites of Hg (ic) with alkaline earths revealed that the combining power of mercuric nitrite was increased as the atomic weight of the other metal decreased²⁶. It was found that the salts had the following compositions:

Next we find him interested in the preparation of nitrites of the mercury-alkyl and-aryl ammonium series^{31, 34, 35-37, 40-41}. He determined the molar conductivity of mono-amine nitrites and found it to be similar to alkali nitrites. The ethylenediamine nitrites behaved like alkaline earth nitrites. The compounds were represented as

Methylammonium nitrite, alkylammonium nitrites, and tetramethylammonium hyponitrite were investigated between 1911 and 1913. Unlike mercuric nitrite, which forms complex salts with alkyl and aryl amines, the double decomposition of silver nitrite with alkyl amine hydrochlorides gave nitrites of the alkylammonium series. The late Professor B. B. Dey was associated with this work^{52-55,57,70}. Professor Dey gave a detailed account of this work in his Acharya Ray memorial lecture¹⁴³. A striking paper was published on the decomposition and sublimation of ammonium nitrite³⁹ in 1912 in collaboration with Professor N. R. Dhar. Ammonium nitrite was found to vaporise undissociated at 80°. The Nature (Aug. 13th, 1912) in reviewing this work remarked that Professor Ray had added to his success in preparing ammonium nitrite in a tangible form and determining the vapour density of this fugitive compound. This paper was read before the Chemical Society, London. Sir William Ramsay and Dr. Veley paid warm tribute to him for his experimental skill. It was admitted that he and his pupils had greatly increased our knowledge of ammonium and amine nitrites.

With the late Professor J. C. Ghosh, the velocity of decomposition and the dissociation constant of nitrous acid was determined⁶¹. A solution of nitrous acid can be obtained at 0° by double decomposition and that it can be concentrated by freezing out the water. It was shown that nitrous acid decomposed with a mono-molecular velocity constant. It was recorded that nitrous acid reacted very slowly with urea. Subsequently, Werner utilised this observation when giving his structure of urea.

Mercuric nitrite reacts with mercaptans to give mercury mercaptide nitrites of the formula RSHgNO_2 and $\text{RSH} \cdot \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_2$. These react with alkyl iodides to give sulphonium compounds conforming to the general formula^{65,66}

The compound I-Hg-S-S-Hg-I was prepared which exhibited remarkable phototropism.

He tried to differentiate between compounds containing SH grouping which he called 'true mercaptans' and those in which a mercaptanic group arises by tautomerism. These

latter, he called, potential mercaptans⁷². With 2,5-dithio-1,3,4-thiadiazole he got trinuclear condensation product which he formulated as $(C_xN_2S_3)_x \cdot Hg_2O$ (where $x=2,3,4$ or 6). These furnished, on interaction with alkyl iodide, long-chain sulphur compounds⁶⁷. These compounds are certainly worth re-investigation. It must be remembered that at that time our knowledge of polymers was still to come. The idea of folding chains and cross linkage formation had yet to be advanced. In view of recent advances in knowledge, it is necessary that the long-chain sulphur compounds described by him should receive further investigation. Phenyl mercaptan gave a mercaptide of the formula Ph_3S_3Hg which yielded the sulphonium compound⁵⁶ of the formula:

The study of these complex mercaptans led him to investigate the formation and behaviour of some simple sulphides and mercaptans. He found that chloropicrin could be used as a diagnostic reagent for differentiating between real and potential mercaptans. The potential mercaptans always parted with some sulphur in the elementary form when it was allowed to react with this reagent. It was shown that thioacetamide and thiocarbamide behaved like real mercaptans⁶⁶. He showed that a simple reaction like the interaction of ethylene dibromide and alcoholic potassium sulphhydrate gave a complex mixture of compounds from which he isolated $HS \cdot (C_2H_4S)_2 \cdot C_2H_4 \cdot SH$ and the corresponding tetrasulphide $(C_2H_4)_3S_4$ along with the trisulphide⁹⁴⁻⁹⁵ of the formula $(C_2H_4S)_3$.

Those who were privileged to see him work in the laboratory could not fail to notice his remarkable skill in separating complex mixtures. His experimental skill was comparable to that of W. H. Perkin (Jun.). There may be many views as to the mechanism of formation of these compounds—he did everything he could to establish their constitutions. All the physico-chemical methods known at that time were pressed into service to prove the structures he assigned to these compounds. He studied the permanganate oxidation of trimethylene tetrasulphide¹⁰⁴ which seemed to support the view he held about this compound.

Triethylene trisulphonc was obtained by permanganate oxidation and a disulphone with nitric acid. Benzylidenediethylene tetrasulphide and benzylidenediethylene trisulphide were obtained by the interaction of dithioglycol and benzylidene chloride. Diethylene di- and tetrasulphides were obtained as byproducts. Therefore, it is clear that the formation of the several byproducts in the reaction between ethylene dibromide and alcoholic potassium sulphhydrate was not due to the presence of polysulphides of potassium present in the alcoholic KSH, which conceivably could have been the case as alcoholic KSH was prepared by the action of H_2S on alcoholic KOH^{94-95, 104-106}. A very interesting series of long-chain sulphur compounds of the type $Br \cdot C_2H_4 \cdot (S \cdot C_2H_4)_n \cdot Br$, was obtained by the interaction of ethylene dibromide and dithioglycol¹⁰⁷. These macro-molecular compounds are certainly worth further investigation by the newer methods of physical-organic chemistry.

Some mercaptans of the purine group were synthesised for the first time¹⁶. Dr. P. K. Bose⁹⁶ was associated with this work. These compounds have acquired new interest as the possibility of their acting as antimetabolites has been suggested recently.

One interesting compound isolated at this time was the compound described as thio-crotonic acid of the constitution^{8c}:

This compound was obtained by the action of thioacetamide on chloroacetic acid in acetone solution. Apparently a molecule of ammonia had been lost in the reaction resulting in the formation of a three-membered ring system consisting of two C atoms and a S atom.

Ethyl thioacetoacetate and ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylate were prepared from the related oxygenated compounds with H_2S and HCl . Acid hydrolysis of alkyl derivatives of the above compounds gave mercaptans and alkaline hydrolysis gave mercapto-crotonic acids¹³⁸.

Double sulphates of sulphonium bases with sulphates of Cu and Mg groups were described¹⁰⁹ and also those of the phosphonium bases¹²¹.

The true nature of valency had puzzled almost everyone before the twenties of the present century. Acharya Ray started a long series of investigations on the valency of Au, Pt, and Ir. He found that with ethylene dithioglycol, platinum chloride formed complexes of the formula $\text{Pt}-(\text{S}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_4-\text{SH})_x$ where $x=3,4,5,6$ or 8 , depending on the experimental condition. Diethyl sulphide reacts with platinum chloride to give (a) $\text{PtCl}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})$, (b) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, (c) $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, (d) $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, and (e) $\text{PtCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The compound (b) was isolated in six isomeric forms and the constitutions of three of these were settled. One was Blomstrand's *cis* compound, the second was the related *trans* compound, and the third was shown to be $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4] \text{PtCl}_4$. The compound (c) was shown to be a molecular mixture of (b) and (d). This was proved by fractional crystallisation from alcohol. The two constituents were treated with ammonia and their constitutions were confirmed. The compound (e) shows a higher co-ordination number than 6. The constitution of these complexes were studied by their action on organic bases and by determining their ionisability¹²².

With mercaptanic radical, Au also forms compounds in which it can behave as a di-, tri-, tetra-, or a pentavalent atom¹²³. An example of bivalent Au is the crystalline compound $2\text{AuCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$. With ethylene thioglycol, gold chloride gave $2\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2$, which was regarded as a compound of Au having an abnormal valency. An example of pentavalent gold was found in the compound $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_3\text{Au}_2$. These claims have been received with indifference, but it may be mentioned that in view of the fact that the compounds of bi-positive and tri-positive silver have now been properly established, it may be worth while to re-investigate these compounds of Ray. Compounds of Ir also received his attention^{134, 137}. The compound $\text{IrCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ was isolated in two forms which were *cis* and *trans* isomers. His last contribution was on the subject of fluoro compounds. By double decomposition of anhydrous thallos fluoride with reactive halogen compounds, ethyl and methyl fluoroformate, fluoroacetone, and fluoroacetal etc. were prepared¹³⁹⁻¹⁴¹.

From the foregoing summary of his work it will be seen that though placed under extremely difficult circumstances he was able to carry on researches mainly designed to train pupils who were to spread chemical knowledge in this country. In this he was eminently successful as many of his pupils later on occupied important chairs all over India and established thriving schools of research. The names of the following may be mentioned.

The late Professors J. C. Ghosh, B. B. Dey, H. K. Sen, R. L. Datta, P. Neogi, R. L. Dey P. C. Mitter, A. C. Ganguli and Professors P. B. Sarkar, P. Ray, J. N. Mukherjee, P. C. Guha, J. N. Ray, P. K. Bose, B. C. Guha and several others, who carried his message to the different parts of India. He had the prophetic vision to see that the independence of this country would be attained soon and if we were to reap the benefits of this emancipation, we must have men who would be able to bear the responsibility that would come. It is for this that we regard him as the greatest benefactor to the community. It will be idle to compare his chemical achievement with that of the great savants of the West. He worked with a mission despite all the humiliation he had to suffer and his greatest achievement was the fulfilment of his mission. A story which Mr. Hemendra Prasad Ghosh, the Editor of the Basumati, related at a public meeting may be recorded here. It was in the early part of this century, when Sir J. C. Bose and Sir P. C. Ray were at the Presidency College, the former was insulted by the then Principal of the College. Tagore, the poet, advised Sir J. C. to resign from the college along with P/C Ray. The National Council of Education (a non-governmental body) would give the scientists facilities for research in a new institution which they would build for them. Bose was all in favour of resigning but Ray advised him not to do so. He was doubtful if another laboratory with necessary equipments could be built easily and it might take ages to build a laboratory. The consequence would be that their researches and training of students would be halted. Therefore, personal insult was considered to be too small a thing in the greater interest of their mission. Had Bose and Ray resigned in 1905, we shudder to think what would have been the state of science in this country now. He was once offered the principalship of a mufasil college. The acceptance of this post would have removed the stigma of his serving as a Provincial Service officer at the Presidency College, but as that mufasil college did not have adequate laboratory facilities, he promptly turned down the offer. Had he elected to accept this post, there would have been no school of chemistry nor probably the Indian Chemical Society.

The foundation of the College of Science with the munificent donations from T. N. Palit and Rash Behari Ghosh realised a long cherished dream of Acharya Ray. The hopes of the authorities of the University that the Government would supplement the resources of the institution by liberal grants did not, however, materialise. The University got a paltry sum of Rs. 12,000/- a year from the Imperial grant for the upkeep of the laboratories. This again had stilted effect on the growth of research activities. Acharya Ray was educated in Scotland and had acquired the thrifty habits of the Scot. Woe betide the student who dared to waste a drop more of the reagent than was necessary or allowed wastage of tap-water. Every economy was effected so that research work did not suffer. I remember when a very junior student, I was greatly interested in the doings of the seniors who were busy doing research work with the Master. I used to stand hours on end in the corridor to get a glimpse of the Professor and his chosen pupils doing research work in the summer holidays of 1915. One day he caught me at my spying and took me inside and questioned me at length. He then immediately assigned me the task of recovering silver from the various residues which he had kept in several bottles collected over the years. After I recovered and showed him the ingot, he had it weighed and told me the value of the material which I had recovered. I was then asked to convert the Ag into AgNO_3 crystals. I remember having prepared quite a few pounds of this material. Next the gold and platinum residues were worked up. From various iodide precipitates, a good amount of iodine was recovered.

He made every student collect in separate bottles all solvent-residues and these had to be recovered. This would give the junior students excellent training and incidentally would reduce the expenses of the laboratory.

Till his last day in the laboratory, he carried on experiments with his own hands. Numerous papers by him without student collaborators would testify to this. His manipulative skill was superb. We used to watch him doing gas analysis fascinated. It was thrilling to watch him transfer minute amount of a gas by the gas pipette.

Much has been said about his teaching methods. He has given an account of his methods of teaching in his autobiography. He believed that "the business of the university was not the transformation of undergraduates into fountains of knowledge. Its business is the difficult task of teaching students how facts are converted into truth. A mind receptive to novelty, capable of wisdom, inclined to moderation—these are the excellences at which it aims. The university has failed when its students are not aroused to passionate discussion amongst themselves or awakened to the study of great books."

Those of us who were privileged to attend his lectures know that he loved to develop a subject historically and gave scant prominence to mere details. His object was to trace the development of human thought. He believed that this approach was the only method to develop the critical faculty in young students. We became intimately acquainted with the past masters like Davy, Faraday, Berzelius, Thomsen, Maxwell, Kekule, Victor Meyer, Ramsay, Rayleigh, and host of other makers of science of the nineteenth century. When we complained about the scanty equipment we had, he would tell us how Berzelius made epoch making discoveries in a small laboratory and his only assistant was the house-maid, Anna. He believed that the personal skill of a man is all that counts, otherwise Berzelius would not have been able to determine the atomic weights with that uncanny accuracy when he had to use an ink-pot as counterpoise. This heartened us a great deal and we took the poor facilities we had as a misfortune of no consequence.

It is well known that he was above everything else a patriot. It occurred to him that the students should know that we had also developed the positive sciences in the past and therefore, we had a responsibility for developing science at the present time. It was with this object that he embarked on the writing of his monumental *History of Hindu Chemistry*. Berthelot had written three volumes on "Syriac, Arabic and Middle Age Alchemy". The impression in Europe had gained ground that India's contribution to Chemistry was insignificant. He threw himself heart and soul to the study of Sanskrit sources in the original. The first volume of *Hindu Chemistry* was published in 1902 and the second volume in 1908. This book received universal encomium abroad and was hailed as a very important contribution to the history of science. This book has been recently revised and enlarged by Professor P. Rây in 1956. The book has been renamed "*History of Chemistry in Ancient and Medieval India*". Acharya Ray himself wanted to revise his book towards the end of his life but advancing years stood in the way. The Indian Chemical Society has thus fulfilled his wishes in publishing this book. The *Nature* while reviewing this book wrote "Since there is much new material in the book, all those who are fortunate enough to have the earlier edition (P. C. Ray's *History of Hindu Chemistry*) will wish to have the new one."

With the growth of research activity in India, it became apparent to him that the time has come to publish a journal of our own as it took a long time to have papers published abroad. It was with this object that the Indian Chemical Society was founded in 1924 and he was elected the 'Founder President' of the Society. In reply to the congratulation from the President and Council of the Chemical Society, London, he wrote "The J. C. S. has hitherto been the only organ of chemists throughout the British Empire, and the Publication Committee have been hard put to it to find space for the ever-increasing number of communications and have often been under the necessity of appealing to authors of papers

to abridge them as far as possible. This will explain the necessity of founding the Indian Chemical Society, with an organ of its own.

"More than forty years ago, while a student at Edinburgh, I almost dreamt a dream that, God willing, a time would come when modern India would also be in a position to contribute her quota to the world's stock of scientific knowledge, and it has been my good fortune to see my dream materialise. I have shown in my 'History of Hindu Chemistry' that this branch of science was jealously pursued in ancient India and I have now the satisfaction of finding chairs of chemistry in most of the Universities of India filled by my own pupils, who have also been regular contributors to the J. C. S. — I can scarcely suppress the feelings which arise in me as I am penning these lines."

From the above it will be seen that his whole life was modelled by the one object of rehabilitating this country which had fallen on very evil days at the time of his birth. It did not fall to his lot to see the attainment of 'Independence' but to the future historian of modern India, he will be one of the few, who helped to usher in the 'New Age'. He did not take active part in politics, but he was always in active sympathy with the vanguard of the fight. He used to tell us how Cannizzaro once did shut up his laboratory and shouldered a musket saying 'science can wait but freedom cannot'. He did not shut up his laboratory, but was always there where wanted. His work in connection with the North Bengal floods is a case in point. The correspondent of the Manchester Guardian wrote:

"My enquiries on the spot made it quite clear that Government have lost immensely in prestige over the whole affair and that Non-cooperation has won what government have lost, thanks to the fine work of Sir P. C. Ray's volunteers".

Some Englishmen said at that time if Gandhi had two more associates of the calibre of Ray, Swaraj would have come that very year.

While feverish activities were going on in connection with relief operation, the work in the laboratory²⁵ continued as usual. This meant extra strain on himself and his students who remained on one duty or another for 14 hours a day. No one grudged putting in this extra amount of work for months on end. Such was his magnetic personality!

Towards the end of his life, when physical handicap stood in the way of his actively working in the laboratory, he used to visit different university-centres where his pupils were engaged in teaching. Dacca, Bangalore, Patna, Allahabad, Madras, Lahore, Bombay, etc. had received frequent visits from him. The students there used to eagerly look forward to these visits. He used to call them affectionately his "grand-pupils". He was in the habit of addressing them and visit them in the laboratory to see them working. Anything new attracted him considerably. I remember once when on a visit to Lahore, he accepted three lecture engagements in an afternoon to my great consternation. He was in very poor health at that time. This touch with the students in various parts of India greatly helped in the spread of chemical knowledge and the torch he kindled thus illuminated the dark corners of many minds in different parts of this sub-continent.

REFERENCES

1. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, p. 53.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, **71**, 337.
3. *Ibid.*, p. 348.
4. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, p. 218.
5. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, **12**, 365.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, **71**, 1097.
7. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, p. 103.
8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, **71**, 1105.
- 9-11. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, p. 239; 1899, p. 23; 1901, p. 96.
12. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, p. 96; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, **81**, 664.
13. *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1894, **59**, 63.
14. *Ibid.*, 1912, **8**, 107.
15. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1903, **72**, 215.
- 16-18. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 523; 1905, **87**, 171, 177.
- 19-20. *Ibid.*, 1905, **87**, 9; 1907, **91**, 1404.
21. *Ibid.*, 1907, **91**, 1405.
- 22-23. *Ibid.*, 1907, **91**, 2031, 2033.
24. *Ibid.*, 1908, **93**, 997.
25. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, p. 75.
26. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 66.
27. *Ibid.*, 1909, **95**, 345.
28. *Ibid.*, 1910, **97**, 326.
29. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, p. 172.
30. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 1012.
31. *Ibid.*, 1911, **99**, 1475.
32. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, p. 258.
33. *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1912, **8**, 103;
34. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 965.
- 35-37. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, p. 292; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 3, 101.
- 38-39. *Ibid.*, 1912, **101**, 319, 1185.
- 40-41. *Ibid.*, 1912, **101**, 616, 1552.
42. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, p. 278.
- 43-45. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **89**, 551; 1907, **91**, 1866
46. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1909, **64**, 184.
47. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 323.
48. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, p. 173.
49. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **89**, 1900.
50. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, p. 246.
51. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 1016.
- 52-55. *Ibid.*, 1911, **99**, 1470; 1912, **101**, 141, 216, 612.
56. *Ibid.*, 1911, **99**, 1972.
57. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, p. 102.
- 58-59. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 491; 1911, **99**, 1466.
- 60-62. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, p. 140; 1914, p. 304, 143.
63. *Chem. News*, 1914, **109**, 85.
64. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 125.
- 65-68. *Ibid.*, 1916, **109**, 131, 603; 1917, **111**, 101; 1919, **115**, 548.
69. *Ibid.*, 1917, **111**, 159.
70. *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1912, **8**, 101.
71. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 507.
72. *Ibid.*, 1919, **115**, 871.
- 73-76. *Ibid.*, 1920, **117**, 1090; 1922, **121**, 323; 1916, **109**, 122.
77. *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1912, **8**, 371.
- 78-81. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 1562; 1916, **109**, 698; 1917, **111**, 510, 417.
- 82-83. *Ibid.*, 1913, **103**, 283; 1914, **105**, 2159.
- 84-86. *Ibid.*, 1919, **115**, 261, 541, 1148.
87. *Ibid.*, 1919, **115**, 1308.
- 88-92. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 1565; 1921, **119**, 1643; 1913, **103**, 1; 1919, **115**, 552; 1924, **125**, 1141.

93. *Ibid.*, 1923, 123, 133.
94-95. *Ibid.*, 1923, 123, 2147; 1922, 121, 1279.
96. *Ibid.*, 1923, 123, 1957.
97-102. *This Journal*, 1925, 2, 178; 1926, 3, 155, 358; 1927, 4, 467; 1928, 5, 139; 1934, 11, 737.
103. *Ibid.*, 1924, 1, 63.
104. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 208.
105. *This Journal*, 1926, 3, 1.
106-108. *Ibid.*, 1926, 3, 73, 75, 23.
109-110. *Ibid.*, 1927, 4, 37; 1928, 5, 69.
111. *Ibid.*, 1927, 4, 89.
112. *Ibid.*, 1928, 5, 527.
113. *Nature*, 1929, 124, 480.
114-119. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 178, 329; 1930, 187, 33; 1933, 211, 62; 1934, 220, 24.
120. *This Journal*, 1928, 5, 733.
121. *Ibid.*, 1929-9, 6, 27.
122. *Ibid.*, 1929, 6, 885.
123. *Ibid.*, 1929, 8, 865.
124. *Ibid.*, 1933, 7, 1.
125. *Nature*, 1930, 126, 310.
126. *This Journal*, 1930, 7, 297.
127. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 187, 121.
128-133. *This Journal*, 1930, 7, 67; 1931, 8, 537, 711, 287, 689, 739.
134-137. *Ibid.*, 1932, 9, 251; 1933, 10, 275; 1934, 11, 51; 1936, 13, 138.
138. *Ibid.*, 1933, 10, 75.
139-141. *Nature*, 1933, 132, 749; *this Journal*, 1935, 12, 93; 1936, 13, 427.
142. *Nature*, 1934, 134, 1010.
143. *Dey, this Journal*, 1949, 25, 433.